

PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLE, TEACHERS' COMMITMENT AND PERFORMANCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Principals' Leadership Style, Teachers' Commitment and Performance among Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The study's main purpose was to examine the school principals' leadership styles, teachers' commitment and performance among secondary schools in the Division of Zambales. There were a total of 470 secondary teachers who served as respondents in this study who have taught during the school year 2021-2022. The Descriptive research design was used to assess the perception of the teachers to assess the leadership styles utilized by the school principals and its relationship on teachers' organizational commitment. The data were gathered from the respondents through a modified-adopted survey questionnaire. The descriptive (frequency, percentage and mean) and inferential statistics (Pearson r and ANOVA) were utilized for the analysis and interpretation of data. The major results showed that the teacher-respondents perceived that the school principal's leadership style as Kayod, leadership style by Libro, leadership style by Ugnayan, and leadership style by Oido are highly practiced while leadership style by Lusot is practiced. The teacher-respondents perceived as Beyond Expected Standard with regard to teachers' organizational commitment in terms of affective commitment while perceived as Approached Expected Standard in terms of continuance commitment and normative commitment. The teacher-respondents are assessed Outstanding on their work performance. There is a highly significant difference on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents' work performance and the school's principal leadership style. There is a highly significant difference on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents' work performance and their organizational commitment. There is a highly significant relationship on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents toward the school's principal leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment. Filipino leadership style by Kayod increased teachers' work performance in terms of quality and time, technical skills and knowledge, originality, creativity, and initiative in the Division of Zambales. The performance of secondary school teachers denotes a high level of achievement and commitment. In the light of the findings, it is recommended that the School heads may adopt leadership style by Kayod, Leadership style by Libro, Leadership style by Ugnayan, and Leadership style by Oido because the combinations of these Filipino leadership styles enables leaders to engage everyone within the organization. Affective commitment can be used by school leaders to represent organizational commitment among teachers. Teachers perform better when they feel that their school head cares about them, they feel respected, act as ambassadors for their organization, and are generally valuable assets. To increase school and teacher performance, school heads can apply Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido leadership style to the team by adopting a range of methods and strategies. The school head may regard and pay proper attention to teachers' views and opinions in order to meet the needs of the entire institution in terms of teaching loads, teaching materials, and other supplies for the instructors to function efficiently. To boost teachers' dedication to their work, school administrators may use the combination of Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido leadership approaches. To raise student achievement, the school principal may employ suitable measures such as prizes and recognition for teachers who are dedicated to their work. A training program to improve organizational change management capacity could be planned by school heads and DepEd officials. The school head may consider to increased teacher participation in policy-making, meeting schedules, discussion of ideas and opinions for the school's progress, and increased student achievement are some of the ways school heads can create a conducive environment that will help improve teachers' performance and satisfaction in the field of teaching.

Keywords: *principals' leadership style, teachers' commitment, performance, secondary schools*

Introduction

Effective principal leadership strategies increase school organization, teaching, and student performance outcomes. These strategies include identifying roles and objectives, framing and expressing a school's goals and mission, and supporting professional growth (Tosh & Doss, 2022). A cheerful community of students and instructors can be found in well-run schools. Their success can be ascribed to their managers' attentive leadership to the requirements of their subordinates. On the other hand, bad leadership can lead to a lack of commitment among instructors in schools that do not do well. However, before reaching such a decision, it is necessary to determine whether the schools have the necessary systems and facilities to run well. It's not unusual to locate schools in rural locations with few or no basic infrastructure. While this may be true, the owners rely on principals and school administration to construct or establish functional organizational structures by giving leadership. One of the most crucial factors in the success of any educational institution is leadership. Setting the vision, mobilizing the entire institution in a focused direction, motivating and inspiring others, and setting the pace by becoming good role models are all examples of good leadership. While a school principal's responsibilities include both leadership and management, there is a clear distinction between the two (Chirchir, Kemboi, Kirui & Ngeno, 2014).

All school leaders are not created equal because there is no single type of educational leadership that is optimal. Leadership abilities

are not only required of principals. Teacher leaders, team leaders, instructional coaches, and other positions benefit from these abilities. All of these jobs demand leadership abilities, but the styles vary greatly depending on the person and the situation (McDonald, 2021). There is implicit recognition of the important role which school management plays in achievement of school goals. Therefore, principals' need to display leadership styles that can enhance teachers' performance thus improve student's achievements (UNESCO, 2016).

The success of any organization is highly rated upon the head, boss or the manager of such an enterprise, like business, school or any organization. The leadership impact is desirable in an organization to aid easy and maximum success. Leadership is an instruction used in an organization for behavior modification. It determines the goals of an organization and means of accomplishing them. Therefore, leadership in an organization has been seen as motivator whereby one person who is the head motivates others towards the achievement of specific goals of the organizations.

Effective leadership role provided by the principal will lead to the achievement of the school's goals and objectives. Education among other concern is an instrument for effecting national development with the formulation of national policy on education. The principals' leadership style in secondary schools is a pointer of the level of productivity of teachers or their job performance. With the close review of the setbacks being experienced in some secondary schools, pressure groups are agitating for effective leadership styles. It is glaring that some principals in Schools Division of Zambales have not considered their styles of leadership as the determinants of teachers' job performance level.

Several researchers have defined leadership style in different contexts, in view of the foregoing, (Chandan, 2017) defines leadership style as the ingredient of personality embodied in leaders that causes subordinates to follow them. Okumbe, (2018) on the other hand defines leadership styles as particular behaviours applied by a leader to motivate subordinates to achieve the objectives of the organization. It refers to the underlying needs of the leader that motivate his behavior (Siskin, 2014; Okeniyi, 2015).

According to Koontz (2018) "If all school principals can rely upon all the subordinates to contribute towards group goal accomplishment with zeal and confidence, there would be no need to develop the act of leadership". There is always the need to boost the morale of teachers, which will even make them to serve to their maximum capability. Therefore, among the administrative functions of the principal is to persuade teachers and use his leadership style to coordinate all activities to ensure they contribute willingly to organizational goals. It is worth knowing that the improvement of any educational institution depends on quality of its teachers. However, there are certain moments and conditions where teachers are unable to engage and give commitment due to invisible influence of the school heads to get them involved.

The main objective of this study was to examine and assess the perception of the secondary school teachers towards leadership styles utilized by the principal in relation to teachers' organizational commitment and performance in the Division of Zambales.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine and assess the perception of secondary school teachers towards principals' leadership styles and teachers' commitment and performance among secondary schools in the Division of Zambales, particularly, school year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do teacher-respondents describe their School Principals' leadership styles in terms of Filipino leadership styles:
 - 1.1. Kayod;
 - 1.2. Libro;
 - 1.3. Lusot;
 - 1.4. Oido;
 - 1.5. Ugnayan?
2. What is level of teachers' organizational commitment in terms of:
 - 2.1. affective commitment;
 - 2.2. continuance commitment; and
 - 2.3. normative commitment?
3. What is the level of teachers' work performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) of Teachers during the SY 2020-2021?
4. Is there a significant difference between the school principal leadership styles and work performance of the teachers?
5. Is there a significant difference between teachers' work performance and teachers' organizational commitment?
6. Is there a significant relationship on school principals' leadership styles and organizational commitment?
7. What theoretical model may be developed from the study?

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative research design will be used to carry out this study to describe, analyze, and interpret data concerning the school principals' leadership styles and teachers' commitment and performance among secondary schools in the new normal, Schools Division

of Zambales for the academic year 2021-2022.

Shuttleworth (2008; Retrieved June 14, 2020) stated that descriptive research design is a valid method for researching specific subjects and as a precursor to more quantitative studies. Whereas, there are some valid concerns about the statistical validity, as long as the limitations are understood by the researcher, this type of study is a valuable scientific tool. Meanwhile, Fraenkel & Wallen (2013) argued that the goal of quantitative methods is to determine whether the predictive generalizations of a theory hold. Thus, quantitative research is more concerned with issues of how much, how well, or to whom that particular issue applies.

The Descriptive method research is a measure of a variable with varying levels of measurement. According to Johnson (2012), this research is appropriate when the researcher would like to make an intervention program based on the data generated from the study to improve the quality and standard of the mentioned indicators in the variable of the study. In this study, principal's leadership style was described.

The researcher used a descriptive analysis method to analyze the high school teachers' work performance, in the Schools Division of Zambales, and used descriptive research design with a questionnaire as the main instrument in gathering data.

Respondents

The Four hundred seventy (470) teacher-respondents from Public Secondary High School, Schools Division of Zambales were the target respondents in this study. The researcher used stratified random sampling technique to represent all the selected school in the entire division of Zambales. Stratified random sampling is typically used by researchers when trying to evaluate data from different subgroups or strata. It allows to quickly obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents used in the study. The subjects of the study were the public high school teachers from School Division of Zambales particularly in High School with four hundred seventy (470) high school teachers each and it includes the following: Sta Cruz District particularly in Lipay High School, Candelaria District particularly in Pamibian Integrated School, Masinloc District particularly Taltal National High School, Palauig District particularly Rofulo Landa High School, Iba District particularly Zambales National High School, Botolan District particularly Botolan National High School, Cabangan District particularly Cabangan National High School, San Felipe District particularly Governor Manuel Barretto National High School, San Narciso District particularly La Paz National High School, San Antonio District particularly San Antonio National High School, San Marcelino District particularly San Guillermo National High School, Castillejos district particularly Castillejos National High School, and Subic District particularly Subic National High School.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Teacher - Respondents from Public Secondary Schools of Division of Zambales*

<i>Secondary High Schools</i>	<i>Teachers (f)</i>
1. Subic National High School	96
2. Castillejos National High School	60
3. San Guillermo National High School	32
4. San Antonio National High School	23
5. La Paz National High School	24
6. Gov. Manuel Barretto National High School	14
7. Cabangan National High School	27
8. Botolan National High School	32
9. Zambales National High School	73
10. Rofulo Landa High School	23
11. Taltal National High School	23
12. Pamibian Integrated School	19
13. Lipay High School	24
Total	470

Instruments

In assessing the principals' leadership style, teachers' commitment and performance, the researcher utilized a modified- adopted survey questionnaire from the survey of school principals' leadership styles and teachers' commitment and performance among secondary schools based on the study of Abid, Saghir, Misbah, & Ayesha (2015). Principal's Leadership Styles and Teachers' Job Satisfaction: A CS at SL. The questionnaire was divided into three parts such as 1.) Principals' leadership styles; 2.) Teacher's work performance; 3.) Teacher's Organizational Commitment. The questionnaire underwent validation and reliability testing for changes, corrections, and suggestions to further improve pilot testing and reliability testing such as Cronbach's alpha reliability test. The data gathered were statistically tested to determine the reliability coefficient of the items.

Procedure

After the validation and reliability testing, the researcher sought the approval of the DepEd-Schools Division of Zambales officials and school administer the questionnaire. A letter of request addressed to the respondents that they may be guided with its confidentiality.

Then a checklist was prepared in agreement with the statement of the problem. The questionnaire was distributed after permission was secured from the management. Retrieval of the questionnaire following strict health protocols (using mask, social distancing, etc.) was followed since it is still pandemic. Tabulation of the gathered data was accomplished and statistical tools were utilized to analyze and interpret the given data. Data gathered was based on the responses collected through a questionnaire that was personally distributed and administered by the researcher with the active participation of the public high school teachers in the division and supportive cooperation of the school heads per district. The survey was distributed to high school teachers in the Division of Zambales.

The privacy of respondents and the confidentiality of the data was ensured. Also, deception about the objectives of this study was avoided. Also, honesty and transparency were observed along with the avoidance of misleading information, the use of offensive, discriminatory, and unacceptable language. Importantly, the researcher followed the APA referencing system in this study. Finally, objective discussions and analysis were maintained.

Data Analysis

The data were gathered through the responses specified in the survey-questionnaire. These were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using statistical software, SPSS Version 28.

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of data and hypothesis testing:

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used in determining the frequency scores and percentages of the respondents.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the perceptions of the respondents on the principal's leadership styles and job indicators on teachers' work performance.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to determine the differences in the perceptions of teachers' work performance and school principals' leadership style. This was also used to determine the difference in the perception of teachers' work performance and the organizational commitment.

The researcher was guided by an arbitrary rule:

Decision Rule 1: If the computed significance (Sig.) value is less than or equal to the 0.05 level of significance ($\text{Sig.} \leq 0.05$), reject the null hypothesis. There is a significant difference.

Decision Rule 2: If the computed significance (Sig.) value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance ($\text{Sig.} \geq 0.05$), accept the null hypothesis. There is a no significant difference.

Decision Rule 3: If the computed significance (Sig.) values is less than or equal to the 0.01 level of significance ($\text{Sig.} \leq 0.01$), reject the null hypothesis. There is a highly significant difference.

Decision Rule 4: If the computed significance (Sig.) values is greater than the 0.01 level of significance ($\text{Sig.} \geq 0.01$), accept the null hypothesis. There is no significant difference.

Pearson Product Moment of Correlation (Pearson R). this was used to determine the relationship between perceptions of teachers on Principal's leadership styles and the job indicators on teachers' work performance. This was used for estimating the relationships among variables.

Likert Scale. In order to facilitate the interpretation of the ratings of the perceptions on leadership styles and job indicators on work performance of teachers, a liker scale will be used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and interpretation of the findings based on collected data, related literature and studies, and the researcher's observations and actual experience.

Assessment of Filipino Leadership Styles

Leadership Style by Kayod

Table 2 presents the use of School Principal's Leadership Style Assessed by Secondary School Teachers as to Kayod

In terms of the Filipino Leadership Styles by Kayod, indicators 3 and 4, School head works seriously to attain organizational goals and School head uses experiences to teach members to become responsible in performing duties (WM=3.62, rank 1.5) interpreted as Highly Practiced. Indicator 1, School head strives for optimal performance (WM=3.57, rank 3) interpreted as Highly Practiced. The overall weighted mean was 3.52 with Qualitative Rating of Highly Practiced. Majority of the school head of the different schools works seriously and uses their experiences to teach members to become responsible in performing their duties.

Table 2. *Principal's Filipino Leadership Styles by Kayod*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School head strives for optimal performance.	3.57	Highly Practiced	3
School head assigns tasks and activities quickly and demand for immediate results.	3.46	Highly Practiced	5
School head works seriously to attain organizational goals.	3.62	Highly Practiced	1.5
School head uses experiences to teach members to become responsible in performing duties.	3.62	Highly Practiced	1.5
School head wants to keep busy all the time.	3.28	Highly Practiced	6
School head reacts to the problem right away and wants to solve it immediately.	3.56	Highly Practiced	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.52	Highly Practiced	

The indicators of Filipino Leadership Styles by Kayod which obtained the least weighted mean were indicator 6, School head reacts to the problem right away and wants to solve it immediately (WM=3.56, rank 4) interpreted as Highly Practiced; indicator 2, School head assigns tasks and activities quickly and demand for immediate result (WM=3.46, rank 5) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicator 5, School head wants to keep busy all the time. (WM=3.28, rank 6) interpreted as Highly Practiced. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Highly Practiced by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and researcher's point of view that Kayod means to give oneself into hard work. Leaders and their leadership qualities have a significant part in the evolution of any institutions. Leadership is the process of influencing the behaviour of people in a manner that they strive willingly and enthusiastically towards the achievement of group objectives. Even before the task begins, leadership must be established. A leader is a person who communicates the policies and plans to the subordinates to start the work (Toppr, 2022). Autocratic leadership involves absolute, authoritarian control over a group. The autocratic style tends to sound quite negative. It certainly can be when overused or applied to the wrong groups or situations. However, autocratic leadership can be beneficial in some instances, such as when decisions need to be made quickly without consulting with a large group of people.

To get things done swiftly and efficiently, some tasks demand strong leadership. When the leader is the most knowledgeable person in the group, the autocratic style can lead to fast and effective decisions (Cherry, 2020).

Leadership Style by Libro

Table 3 presents the use of School Principal's Leadership Style Assessed by Secondary School Teachers as to Libro.

Table 3. *School Principal's Filipino Leadership Styles by Libro*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School head does what the manuals and other formal documents say in making decisions.	3.34	Highly Practiced	8
School head deals with staff when things go wrong and need to create strategy to keep the project running.	3.53	Highly Practiced	4
School head takes time to weigh evidence, explore alternatives, test assumptions and evaluate the soundness of the decision.	3.40	Highly Practiced	7
School head follows systematic and analytic processes to determine what should be done and how to do it.	3.48	Highly Practiced	5
School head consults readings first before deciding on matters affecting the organization.	3.47	Highly Practiced	6
School head believes that training can and should be given for professional growth.	3.65	Highly Practiced	1
School head encourages teachers to solve classroom problems and give them coaching when necessary.	3.61	Highly Practiced	2
School head integrates various styles of management depending on the need of organization.	3.54	Highly Practiced	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Highly Practiced	

In terms of the Filipino Leadership Styles by Libro, indicators 6, School head believes that training can and should be given for professional growth (WM=3.65, rank 1) interpreted as Highly Practiced. Indicator 7, School head encourages teachers to solve classroom problems and give them coaching when necessary (WM=3.61, rank 2) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicator 8, School head integrates various styles of management depending on the need of organization (WM=3.54, rank 3) interpreted as Highly Practiced. The overall weighted mean was 3.50 with Qualitative Rating of Highly Practiced. Majority of the school head believes that training should be given priority for professional growth. Nowadays, neophyte teachers need to undergo training/writeshop to enhance their skills and knowledge specially on the aspect of pedagogy.

The indicators of Filipino Leadership Styles by Libro which obtained the least weighted mean were indicator 5, School head consults

readings first before deciding on matters affecting the organization (WM=3.47, rank 6) interpreted as Highly Practiced; indicator 3, (WM=3.40, rank 7) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicator 3, School head does what the manuals and other formal documents say in making decisions (WM=3.34, rank 8) interpreted as Highly Practiced. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Highly Practiced by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of teachers and researcher's point of view that leadership styles by Libro are characterized by reflecting on the problem first before acting on them, a technocrat relying on the authority of facts and statistics. A distinction is often made between management style (around organization and process) and leadership style (more strategic and inspirational.) Great leadership is expected at the top of an organization rather than competent management but it can be difficult to define what great leadership actually is. Therefore, American managers are more likely to disregard the opinions of subordinates than managers in other, more consensus or compromise- oriented cultures. This can obviously rise to frustrations, which can occasionally appear to boil over in meetings (Warburton, 2022).

Leadership Style by Lusot

Table 4. School Principal's Filipino Leadership Styles by Lusot

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
School head ensures that teachers are performing well.	3.60	Highly Practiced	1
School head breaks rules of the organization to make decisions.	2.93	Practiced	7
School head is better at feeling the intentions of the subordinates.	3.25	Practiced	3
School head wants the least hardship and sweat, paying off problems and making short cuts.	2.97	Practiced	6
School head solves problems through compromises and easy settlements.	3.12	Practiced	4
School head expects teachers to be available whenever they are needed.	3.37	Highly Practiced	2
School head is rule-oriented rather than result-oriented.	3.05	Practiced	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.18	Practiced	

Table 4 presents the use of School Principal's Leadership Style Assessed by Secondary School Teachers as to Lusot.

In terms of the Filipino Leadership Styles by Libro, indicator 1, School head ensures that teachers are performing well (WM=3.60, rank 1) interpreted as Highly Practiced. Indicator 6, School head expects teachers to be available whenever they are needed (WM=3.37, rank 2) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicator 3, School head is better at feeling the intentions of the subordinates (WM=3.25, rank 3) interpreted as Practiced. The overall weighted mean was 3.18 with Qualitative Rating of Practiced. Majority of the school head ensures that the teachers are performing well. School heads keep on monitoring their teachers as well as the progress of the students.

The indicators of Filipino Leadership Styles by Libro which obtained the least weighted mean were indicator 7, School head is rule-oriented rather than result-oriented (WM=3.05, rank 5) interpreted as Practiced; indicator 4, School head wants the least hardship and sweat, paying off problems and making short cuts (WM=2.97, rank 7) interpreted as Practiced and indicator 2, School head breaks rules of the organization to make decisions (WM=2.93, rank 7) interpreted as Practiced. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Practiced by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and researcher's point of view that the principal of the school will always look for loopholes to escape hard work or provide an excuse for failure. Given to taking shortcuts and using unorthodox or even illegal methods to achieve goals. Where rule-breaking is informally permitted, it takes on a routine aspect; where it is not, conflict arises. The hierarchical structure of bureaucracy is mirrored by an organizational hierarchy of rule-breaking. Rule-breaking can be undertaken by individuals acting alone, it can be coordinated by workgroups, or it can be organized by top management as a matter of unofficial policy. When these two dimensions of rule-breaking interact, it becomes clear how such acts vary in response to a wide range of organizational cross-pressures (Martin, Lopez, Roscigno & Hodson, 2013). Making rules and procedures easier to follow improves human performance. Use it to identify whether procedures are being followed and how they might be improved with supervisors and their personnel. Procedures do not always reflect work as done, and people may find themselves in situations where the job cannot get done if rules and procedures are followed. Use it with managers to clarify the organization's policy and system for managing unsafe acts and learning from incidents. Use it to discover if procedures are being followed and how they might be improved with supervisors and their personnel (Energy Institute, 2022).

Leadership Style by Oido

Table 5 presents the use of School Principal's Leadership Style Assessed by Secondary School Teachers as to Oido.

In terms of the Filipino Leadership Styles by Oido, indicator 7, School head gives regular feedback both complimentary and corrective which is essential in shaping desired results (WM=3.45, rank 1) interpreted as Highly Practiced. Indicator 6, School head thinks and acts accordingly in different situations (WM=3.44, rank 2) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicator 4 School head integrates various styles of management and experiences to answer the needs and conditions of the organization (WM=3.36, rank 3) interpreted as Practiced. The overall weighted mean was 3.32 with Qualitative Rating of Highly Practiced. Majority of the school head gives

regular feedback both complimentary and corrective in shaping the desired goals for the betterment of the institution. School heads believe that soliciting ideas and information from the teachers will give higher performance of the entire institution.

Table 5. *School Principal's Filipino Leadership Styles by Oido*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School head relies mostly in practical experiences rather than what the books or any formal documents say in terms of managing the organization.	3.26	Highly Practiced	6
School head believes that the vast field of practical experiences will compensate the lack of formal management education.	3.17	Practiced	8
School heads sees to it that subordinates feel confident on the decisions made.	3.35	Highly Practiced	4.5
School head integrates various styles of management and experiences to answer the needs and conditions of the organization.	3.36	Highly Practiced	3
School head reconciles philosophies and beliefs towards role expectations and tasks in the organization.	3.35	Highly Practiced	4.5
School head thinks and acts accordingly in different situations.	3.44	Highly Practiced	2
School head gives regular feedback both complimentary and corrective which is essential in shaping desired results.	3.45	Highly Practiced	1
School head makes mostly of the decisions and expects employees to put the decisions into actions.	3.23	Practiced	7
Overall Weighted Mean	3.32	Highly Practiced	

The indicators of Filipino Leadership Styles by Oido which obtained the least weighted mean were indicator 1, School head relies mostly in practical experiences rather than what the books or any formal documents say in terms of managing the organization (WM=3.26, rank 6) interpreted as Highly Practiced; indicator 8, School head makes mostly of the decisions and expects employees to put the decisions into actions (WM=3.23, rank 7) interpreted as Practiced and indicator 2, School head believes that the vast field of practical experiences will compensate the lack of formal management education (WM=3.17, rank 8) interpreted as Practiced. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Practiced by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and researcher's point of view that this manager honed his managerial talents by playing it by ear. He depends on practical experience to compensate for his lack of normal management education. Leaders must have a thorough understanding of their talents to connect, communicate, and share from their hearts. They must be willing to provide useful comments as well as receive candid feedback. Critical conversations build relationships and personalized team collaboration achievements. And, leaders must always be able to construct a personal vision for themselves, for their groups, and for the organization. Leaders need to enhance social capabilities and connections through human development programs that are based on face-to-face learning activities and workshops. These learning opportunities assist leaders develop personal self-awareness and practical skills so they can make a difference in their organizations (Fein, 2019). Breakthrough experiences are those that make a significant difference in a leader's development. A key experience inventory assists organizations in identifying the events that are critical to senior leadership success in their organization, allowing them to close developmental gaps and maximize their chances for future success. The key experiences required for your organization to meet its strategic goals and aspirations. Consider how the role is changing and what will be expected of it in three to five years. Understand the experiences that have helped your best leaders succeed. Identify and close experiential gaps for important high-potential leaders to expedite leadership development (Ratanjee, 2018).

Leadership Style by Ugnayan

Table 6 presents the use of School Principal's Leadership Style Assessed by Secondary School Teachers as to Ugnayan.

Table 6. *School Principal's Filipino Leadership Styles by Ugnayan*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
School head thinks first on matters affecting the organization.	3.47	Highly Practiced	3.5
School head believes that participation and coordination make the group cohesive in performing their duties and responsibilities.	3.51	Highly Practiced	1
School head achieves positive results by discussing the matters with the staff.	3.47	Highly Practiced	3.5
School head is interested in what, how and why to do things.	3.48	Highly Practiced	2
School head allows teachers to make decisions and work them in advance to work out the type of decisions each is responsible.	3.38	Highly Practiced	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.46	Highly Practiced	

In terms of the Filipino Leadership Styles by Ugnayan, indicator 2, School head believes that participation and coordination make the group cohesive in performing their duties and responsibilities (WM=3.51, rank 1) interpreted as Highly Practiced. Indicator 4, School head is interested in what, how and why to do things (WM=3.48, rank 2) interpreted as Highly Practiced and indicators 1 and 3, School head thinks first on matters affecting the organization and School head achieves positive results by discussing the matters with the staff

(WM=3.47, rank 3.5) interpreted as Highly Practiced. The overall weighted mean was 3.46 with Qualitative Rating of Highly Practiced. Majority of the school head believes that participation and coordination make the group cohesive in performing their duties and responsibilities.

The indicators of Filipino Leadership Styles by Ugnayan, which obtained the least weighted mean was indicator 5, School head allows teachers to make decisions and work them in advance to work out the type of decisions each is responsible (WM=3.38, rank 5) interpreted as Highly Practiced. This indicator was the least from the rank, however still was assessed and perceived to be Highly Practiced by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of teachers and researcher's point of view that this type of management prefers to be addressed as a peer to his or her subordinates rather than as a boss. It recognizes and emphasizes the relationship and connectivity of manager and subordinates in which collaboration of these two is essential and achieving their desired goal. A key to a successful management is a good relationship between the manager and his/her subordinates. Instead of being a self-centric, valuing others is important for the organization's betterment because working with them is the reason why an organization is continuously operating in the field. It is good to build trust with the working staffs (Espinal, 2018). Leaders who use a "collaborative" leadership style involve their employees in decision-making. An administrator establishing a teacher academy would survey teachers on what they needed to improve student achievement, for example, deciding together what might be most practical and effective. Participative leaders work with staff to guide school programs by learning about a concept or strategy and directing its implementation. They then experiment with classroom implementation alongside teachers, parents, and students and solicit suggestions for continuous improvement (Murphy, 2021).

Summary

Table 7 shows the summary on the use school's principal leadership styles assessed by secondary school teachers.

Table 7. Summary Table on School's Principal Leadership Styles as Assessed by the Secondary School Teachers

<i>Assessment of School's Principal Leadership Styles</i>	<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Leadership Style by Kayod	3.52	Highly Practiced	1
Leadership Style by Libro	3.50	Highly Practiced	2
Leadership Style by Lusot	3.18	Practiced	5
Leadership Style by Oido	3.32	Highly Practiced	4
Leadership Style by Ugnayan	3.46	Highly Practiced	3
Grand Mean	3.40	Highly Practiced	

The summary on the perceptions in the Use of School's Principal Leadership Styles assessed by the Secondary School Teachers result was ranked 1 (OWM=3.52) on Leadership Style by Kayod with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Highly Practiced; followed by Leadership Styles by Libro (OWM=3.50) ranked 2 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Highly Practiced; and Leadership Style by Ugnayan (OWM=3.46), ranked 3 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Highly Practiced. The Grand Mean was 3.40 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Highly Practiced. The teacher-respondents appraised that the Leadership Style by Kayod, Leadership Style by Libro, and Leadership Style by Ugnayan was Highly Practiced. Being an effective leader that embodies Filipino leadership values is nevertheless subject to health issues, particularly in the midst of the epidemic. Working in a remote setup proved difficult because people are accustomed to face-to-face interactions. "With great power comes great responsibility," as the famous Spiderman slogan goes, that being a leader entails not only the obligation of commanding others to achieve objectives, but also the burden of taking care of oneself, both physically and mentally. As a result, mental health is critical for an individual's ability to perform efficiently (Fortes & Evangelista, 2021). This type of leadership makes use of each follower's full potential in order to increase their performance. A good leader must have the qualities of fellowship (kapwa), charm, and empathy (individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational, motivational, and idealized influence). A transformational leader constructs an environment that aims to make a difference and foster success (Ng & Rivera, 2018).

Teacher's Organizational Commitment

Affective Commitment

Table 8 presents Organizational Commitment as Perceived by Secondary School Teachers as to Affective commitment.

In terms of the Affective Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, indicator 6, I am proud to tell others that I am part of my school (WM=3.51, rank 1) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard. Indicator 10, I take the school's policies seriously (WM=3.45, rank 2) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard and indicator 9, I feel that the school's successes are equivalent to my own successes (WM=3.43, rank 3) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard. The overall weighted mean was 3.35 with Qualitative Rating of Beyond Expected Standard.

The indicators of the Affective Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, which obtained the least weighted mean was indicator 1, I still happy no matter how hard my work is here (WM=3.29, rank 8) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard. Indicator 2, I find that my values and organizations values are similar (WM=3.27, rank 9) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard

and Indicator 5, I sign up or volunteer for additional training or responsibilities (WM=3.13, rank 10) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. Majority of the teacher-respondents that they are proud to tell others that they are part of the institution. Perhaps, teachers feel at ease in the organization because their own beliefs and goals align with the school's mission and vision.

Table 8. Teacher's Organizational Commitment as to Affective Commitment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
I still happy no matter how hard my work is here.	3.29	Beyond Expected Standard	8
I find that my values and organizations values are similar.	3.27	Beyond Expected Standard	9
I perceive the school as the best one among the others.	3.34	Beyond Expected Standard	6
I accomplish the job with enthusiasm.	3.33	Beyond Expected Standard	7
I sign up or volunteer for additional training or responsibilities.	3.13	Approached Expected Standard	10
I am proud to tell others that I am part of my school.	3.51	Beyond Expected Standard	1
I demonstrate stronger affiliations to my school.	3.40	Beyond Expected Standard	4
I do not say anything negative or critical toward our school Principal or the School.	3.37	Beyond Expected Standard	5
I feel that the school's successes are equivalent to my own successes.	3.43	Beyond Expected Standard	3
I take the school's policies seriously.	3.45	Beyond Expected Standard	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.35	Beyond Expected Standard	

These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Beyond and Approached Expected Standard by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and researcher's point of view that affective commitment is found when an employee feels like their personal values and priorities are in line with the company's mission and feel at home in the organization. Developing organizational commitment, the bond that employees feel towards their organization, can help employees feel important, connect with their colleagues, and improve productivity (Werf, 2020). According to the study conducted by Hulpia, Devos, Rosseel and Vlerick (2012) explained that distributed leadership can be split into four dimensions: leadership function quality and distribution, quality and distribution of supervision, cooperation within the leadership team, and the teacher participation in decision-making. By understanding the influence of these. It may aid in understanding the effects of distributed leadership on teacher affective commitment. Teacher attrition and turnover were reduced as a result of their increased dedication.

Continuance Commitment

Table 9 presents Organizational Commitment as Perceived by Secondary School Teachers as to Continuance commitment.

Table 9. Teacher's Organizational Commitment: Continuance Commitment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
I continue to work here as long as I get good treatment from the organization.	3.49	Beyond Expected Standard	1
I am afraid of what will happen if I leave my job today.	3.11	Approached Expected Standard	5
I could not leave my organization even if I wanted to leave right now.	3.06	Approached Expected Standard	6
It would be of too much cost if I will immediately leave my organization.	2.98	Approached Expected Standard	8
Staying with my organization right now is a matter of necessity and desire.	3.17	Approached Expected Standard	4
I feel that I have few options to select other jobs if I will leave this organization.	2.85	Approached Expected Standard	9
I feel that I have no alternative jobs to select if I will leave this organization.	2.78	Approached Expected Standard	10
The primary reason I sustained working is that leaving my current work would require personal sacrifice considering the benefits offered by the organization.	3.02	Approached Expected Standard	7
I am loyal to this school.	3.40	Beyond Expected Standard	2
There is much to be picked up by staying with this organization.	3.25	Approached Expected Standard	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.11		

In terms of the Continuance Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, indicator 1, I continue to work here as long as I get good treatment from the organization (WM=3.49, rank 1) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard. Indicator 9, I am loyal to this school (WM=3.40, rank 2) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard and indicator 10, There is much to be picked up by staying with this organization (WM=3.25, rank 3) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. The overall weighted mean was 3.11 with Qualitative Rating of Approached Expected Standard. The majority of respondents continue to work as long as they are treated well by their employers. Teachers may choose to stay in the organization because they are compensated with love, caring, and support from it.

The indicators of the Continuance Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, which obtained the least weighted mean was indicator 4, It would be of too much cost if I will immediately leave my organization (WM=2.98, rank 8) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. Indicator 6, I feel that I have few options to select other jobs if I will leave this organization (WM=2.85,

rank 9) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard and Indicator 7, I feel that I have no alternative jobs to select if I will leave this organization (WM=2.78, rank 10) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still were assessed and perceived to be Approached Expected Standard by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and the researcher's point of view that continuance commitment refers to how motivated employees are to continue with their company/institution. Strong organizational commitment in terms of continuance commitment can improve work performance in terms of IPCRF of the teachers. When the teachers are satisfied with their environment/organization, perhaps their work performance will increase and will stay focus on their task/goal. Therefore, teacher work performance has significant influence with regard to teacher commitment. In employees that are continuance committed, the underlying reason for their commitment lies in their need to stay with the organization. According to the study conducted by Khan, Naseem & Masood (2016) that looked into the impact of long-term commitment and organizational cynicism on employee work satisfaction. Based on current research, we believe that employee job satisfaction is directly tied to staff commitment. Satisfaction and continuance commitment is associated with organizational cynicism. If there is more organizational cynicism, then employees are less satisfied in their organization and it is also related to continuance commitment. The findings of this study showed that corporate cynicism and continued commitment have an evident impact on employee work satisfaction. Moreover, sustaining the satisfaction level of employee is a continuous process whose foundations are intricately linked with the organizational cynicism. The fact that instructors choose to work in cities, according to Akyol, Atan, Gokemen (2013) explains the disparity. Generally, all teachers want to work in city centers. Those who work in rural areas wish to be appointed to schools in city centers. They can state that teachers working in city centers have high continuance commitment levels because they are satisfied with their place of duty. Organizational commitment in educational institutions refers to teachers' effectiveness, job satisfaction, and internal motivation and desire. Primary school teachers, therefore, need to be devoted to their organization, profession and students to be able to work effectively and productively. The more this dedication, the more likely teachers are to succeed (Erdogan & Cavh, 2019).

Normative Commitment

Table 10 presents Organizational Commitment as Perceived by Secondary School Teachers as to Normative.

In terms of the Normative Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, indicator 3, I believe that employee must be loyal to the organization (WM=3.36, rank 1) interpreted as Beyond Expected Standard. Indicator 4, The reason I continue working today is that I feel a sense of moral obligations to the organization (WM=3.23, rank 2) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard and indicator 6, I think that it is reasonable to be a company person in the organization. (WM=3.16, rank 3) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. The overall weighted mean was 2.94 with Qualitative Rating of Approached Expected Standard. Majority of the respondents believe that teachers must be loyal to the organization. Teachers should have a feeling of commitment to the organization; even if they are unhappy with the task/role assigned to them, or if they wish to explore greater chances, they should stay because it is the right thing to do for them.

Table 10. *Teacher's Organizational Commitment: Normative Commitment*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
I feel obliged to pay back for this organization.	2.86	Approached Expected Standard	8
I think that it is not proper these days to transfer from one organization to another.	2.87	Approached Expected Standard	7
I believe that employee must be loyal to the organization.	3.36	Beyond Expected Standard	1
The reason I continue working today is that I feel a sense of moral obligations to the organization.	3.23	Approached Expected Standard	2
Things will be better in days when employee stick to one organization for most of their careers.	3.14	Approached Expected Standard	4
I think that it is reasonable to be a company person in the organization.	3.16	Approached Expected Standard	3
I would not feel it right to leave my present organization and considered better offer outside.	2.95	Approached Expected Standard	5
I could just as well be working for a different organization as long as the type of work was similar.	2.88	Approached Expected Standard	6
Deciding to work for this organization was a definite mistake on my part.	2.38	Approached Expected Standard	10
It would not take very little change in my present circumstances to cause me to leave this organization.	2.58	Approached Expected Standard	9
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94		

The indicators of the Normative Commitment/aspect of Teacher's Organizational Commitment, which obtained the least weighted mean was indicator 1, I feel obliged to pay back for this organization (WM=2.86, rank 8) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. Indicator 10, It would not take very little change in my present circumstances to cause me to leave this organization (WM=2.58, rank 9) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard and Indicator 9, Deciding to work for this organization was a definite mistake on my part. (WM=2.38, rank 10) interpreted as Approached Expected Standard. These indicators were the least from the rank, however still

were assessed and perceived to be Approached Expected Standard by teacher-respondents.

Based on the assessment of the teachers and researcher's point of view that you believe that staying with your company is the correct thing to do. This sense of commitment can arise from a variety of sources. You may believe that staying with your company is a good idea since it has invested money or time in your training. Team members who are simply committed to the status quo may become bored and unmotivated, and no leader wants a team like that! You can reduce your reliance on continuance and normative commitments by being a better leader, working on your general team management skills, and thinking carefully about how your actions might influence your team members. And some people will likely feel a sense of normative commitment if their organization has invested a lot in their training and development (Mindtools, 2022).

Summary

Table 11 shows the summary on the organizational commitment as perceived by secondary school teachers

The summary on the perceptions on the organizational commitment as perceived by Secondary School Teachers result was ranked 1 (OWM=3.35) on Affective Commitment with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Beyond Expected Standard; followed by Continuance Commitment (OWM=3.11) ranked 2 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Approached Expected Standard; and Normative Commitment (OWM=2.94), ranked 3 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Approached Expected Standard. The Grand Mean was 3.13 with qualitative rating/descriptive equivalent of Approached Expected Standard.

Table 11. *Summary on the Organizational Commitment as Perceived by Secondary School Teachers*

<i>Organizational Commitment</i>	<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Affective Commitment	3.35	Beyond Expected Standard	1
Continuance Commitment	3.11	Approached Expected Standard	2
Normative Commitment	2.94	Approached Expected Standard	3
Grand Mean	3.13	Approached Expected Standard	

The teacher-respondents appraised that the affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment was Approached Expected Standard. The findings showed a very high degree of openness on school climate in terms of supportive principal behavior; engaged teacher behavior; and intimate teacher behavior. Feeder high school teachers were all of the times committed to their schools in terms of affective commitment. Finally, the climate of MSU feeder high schools was found to be strongly linked to teachers' organizational commitment. Hence, it is concluded that MSU feeder high schools are institutions characterized as having conducive working-learning both teachers and students in a positive environment (Baoc-Daguisonan, 2018). Teacher participation in decision-making have positive and significant effect on teacher affective communication. The largest influence comes from teacher participation in decision-making, followed by cooperation within the leadership team, quality and allocation of leadership functions, and least from quality and distribution of supervision (Muthiah, Adams, & Abdullah, 2019).

Teachers' Work Performance

Table 12 presents teachers' work performance assessed by secondary school teachers in terms of IPCRF.

Table 12. *Assessment of Teachers' Work Performance in terms of IPCRF*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Qualitative Rating</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
4.500-5.000	Outstanding	452	96.17
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	18	3.83
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory	0	0.00
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0.00
below 1.499	Poor	0	0.00
Total		470	100.00
Mean	4.72	Outstanding	

Out of four hundred seventy (470) teacher-respondents, 452 or 96.17% have a performance rating of 4.500 to 5.000 interpreted as Outstanding and 18 or 3.83% have a rating performance of 3.500 to 4.499 interpreted as Very Satisfactory. The computed mean rating was 4.72 interpreted as Outstanding. The level of work performance of Secondary School Teachers in the Division of Zambales was Outstanding.

Based on the assessment of the teachers' work performance, in terms of quality and time, technical skills and knowledge, originality, creativity, and initiative, performance denotes a high level of achievement and commitment. Teachers at this level of performance should have proven great job mastery across the board. Teachers accomplishments and contributions to the organizations in the Division of Zambales are outstanding. The Teachers' overall performance suggested that they were able to do a good job in the teaching-learning process, starting activities that encourage parents and community people to participate, and keeping up to date by attending seminars, workshops, and conferences. Teachers, on the other hand, were good or outstanding at monitoring and evaluating students' progress

outside of class hours and providing remedial education for slow learners (Baluyos, Rivera, & Baluyos, 2019). Through the mediation of the quality of working life, high-performance work systems directly and indirectly influence teachers' in-role performance and extra-role behavior. The relationship between high-performance work systems and employee work behaviors is mediated by the quality of work life (Song, Bae, Park & Kim, 2018).

Analysis of Variance on the Difference Between Teachers' Work Performance and Filipino Leadership styles

Table 13. *Analysis of Variance on the Difference in Teachers' Work Performance as Affected by Filipino Leadership Styles*

	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Leadership Styles	Between Groups	19.465	25	.779	7.472	.000	Fail to reject Ho
	Within Groups	46.263	444	.104			
	Total	65.728	469				

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results in Table 13 suggest that there is a highly significant difference in the teachers' work performance in terms of Filipino leadership styles. The computed F value is greater than the critical F value at the 5% and 1% level of significance. The p-value is less than or equal to the alpha value of 0.01

Filipino leadership styles are predictor of teachers' work performance among secondary school teachers in the Division of Zambales. The teachers' work performance results were significant by the Filipino leadership styles of school principal. There is sufficient evidence that Filipino leadership styles has a significant difference on teachers work performance. When the principal's management is good and orderly it can definitely give good performance on the part of the teachers. The leadership style used by the principal has a great deal to do with increasing the work performance of teachers.

A study found that the decision-making approach and leadership style of head teachers have a substantial impact on teachers' task performance in the schools studied. Furthermore, the communication abilities of head teachers have a substantial impact on teachers' work performance in the area. It is necessary to implement proper managerial conduct in order to raise instructors' morale and help them achieve excellent task performance (Mbon, 2017).

Analysis of Variance on the Difference Between Teachers' Work Performance and Teachers' Organizational Commitment

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results in Table 14 suggest that there is a highly significant difference in the teachers' work performance in terms of teachers' organizational commitment. The computed F value is greater than the critical F value at the 5% and 1% level of significance. The p-value is less than or equal to the alpha value of 0.01

Table 14. *Analysis of Variance on the Difference in Teachers' Work Performance as Affected by Teachers' Organizational Commitment*

	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Organizational Commitment	Between Groups	25.137	25	1.005	6.437	.000	Ho is rejected
	Within Groups	69.353	444	.156			Significant
	Total	94.490	469				

The teachers' organizational commitment is a predictor of teachers' work performance among secondary school teachers in the Division of Zambales. The teachers' work performance results were affected by the teachers' organizational commitment.

The findings revealed that the principal's decision-making, organizational commitment, and school climate had both a partial and simultaneous positive and significant effect on the performance of secondary school teachers. The findings of this study can be used by educational administrators at vocational high schools to develop school strategies and policies that will support greater teacher performance and improve school productivity (Mailool, Kartowagiran, Retnowati, Wening & Putranta, (2020). The findings reveal that a performance management procedure' perceived strength is negatively related to teacher weariness while positively related to their performance. Furthermore, the link between perceived performance management process strength and teacher performance appeared to be indirect, with affective organizational commitment serving as the primary mediator (Waeyenberg, Peccei & Decramer, 2020).

Pearson r Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between the School's Principal Leadership Styles and Teachers' Organizational Commitment

Table 15 shows the relationship between school's principal leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment.

As indicated in Table 15, the computer-generated sig value of 0.00 was less than 0.01 alpha level of significance, therefore, the Null Hypothesis is rejected, hence there is significant relationship on the use of school's principal leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment as perceived by the secondary school teachers.

The findings show that at 1% significance level, the data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is significant relationship on the assessment used by the teachers have a Very High Positive Correlation as perceived by teacher-respondents.

Table 15. *Pearson r Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between School’s Principal Leadership Styles and Teachers’ Organizational Commitment*

Source of Variation		Filipino Leadership Styles	Organizational Commitment	Interpretation
Filipino Leadership Styles	Pearson r Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.614**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	
	N	470	470	
Organizational Commitment	Pearson r Correlation Coefficient	.614**	1.000	Ho is rejected Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	
	N	470	470	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As indicated in Table 15, the computer-generated sig value of 0.00 was less than 0.01 alpha level of significance, therefore, the Null Hypothesis is rejected, hence there is significant relationship on the use of school’s principal leadership styles and teachers’ organizational commitment as perceived by the secondary school teachers.

The findings show that at 1% significance level, the data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is significant relationship on the assessment used by the teachers have a Very High Positive Correlation as perceived by teacher-respondents.

It is feasible to increase the educational system's performance through enhancing teachers' working circumstances and finding answers to their work-related issues. These teachers will benefit from the enhancements as well .Encourage them to gain skills and knowledge and put them into practice through professional and organizational dedication (Erdogan & Cavh, 2019).The impact of leadership styles on employee performance was discovered by (Koech and Namusonge, 2012), who recommended that managers abandon their laissez-faire leadership style by becoming more involved in guiding their subordinates; public managers should formulate and implement effective reward and recognition systems. It discovered a link between transformational leadership qualities and teacher effectiveness. In terms of transactional leadership dimensions, the findings revealed that transactional leadership has an impact on the outcome variable, although it is less powerful than transformational leadership (Kashagate, 2013).

Theoretical Model Developed

Figure 1 below shows the Krishma’s Theoretical Model developed based on the findings of the study. The leadership style by Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan and Oido which are highly practiced by the school principals in secondary schools as perceived by the teachers are highly linked to increased teacher’s performance in terms of quality and time, technical skills and knowledge, originality, creativity, initiative and affective commitment as beyond expected standards as perceived by the teachers in meeting their organizational goals. The leadership styles by Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido have increased teacher performance and strengthen their commitment to professional growth. It is critical to improve overall organizational commitment because teachers who show high organizational commitment will engage in positive work behavior. High effective teachers are capable of providing high quality education and assisting students in achieving academic success.

Figure 1. *Krishma’s Theoretical Model*

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that:

The teacher-respondents perceived that the school principals' leadership styles as to Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido are Highly Practiced while perceived as Practiced in terms of leadership style by Lusot.

The teacher-respondents assessed their organizational commitment as Beyond Expected Standard in terms of affective commitment while perceived as Approached Expected Standard in terms of continuance commitment and normative commitment.

The teacher-respondents are assessed "Outstanding" on their work performance with a computed mean rating of 4.72.

There was a highly significant difference on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents' work performance and the school's principal leadership style.

There was a highly significant difference on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents' work performance and their organizational commitment.

There was a highly significant relationship on the perceived level of agreement of teacher-respondents towards the school's principal leadership styles and teachers' organizational commitment.

The leadership styles by Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido have increased teacher performance and strengthen their commitment to professional growth. It is critical to improve overall organizational commitment because teachers who show high organizational commitment will engage in positive work behavior. High effective teachers are capable of providing high quality education and assisting students in achieving academic success.

In the light of the foregoing conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were advanced:

The school head may adopt leadership style by Kayod, Leadership style by Libro, Leadership style by Ugnayan, and Leadership style by Oido because the combinations of these Filipino leadership styles enables leaders to engage everyone within the organization.

Affective commitment can be used by school leaders to represent organizational commitment among teachers. When teachers are emotionally invested, they feel respected, act as ambassadors for their organization, and are generally valuable assets.

School head may apply Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido to increase teacher performance and adopting a range of methods and strategies. The school head may regard and pay proper attention to teachers' views and opinions in order to meet the needs of the entire institution in terms of teaching loads, teaching materials, and other supplies for the instructors to function efficiently.

School administrator may use the combination of Kayod, Libro, Ugnayan, and Oido leadership approaches to boost teachers' dedication to their work.

The school principal may employ suitable measures such as prizes and recognition for teachers who are dedicated to their work to raise student achievement,

A training program to improve organizational change management capacity could be planned by school heads and DepEd officials.

School heads may consider to create a conducive environment that will help improve teachers' performance and satisfaction in the field of teaching through increased teacher participation in policy-making, meeting schedules, discussion of ideas and opinions for the school's progress, and increased student achievement.

A replication study might be conducted to see how school principals' leadership styles affect teachers' commitment.

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